

Some Molecular Adducts of Dibenzyltellurium(IV) Derivatives with Nitrogen Donor Molecules

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Although dibenzyltellurium(IV) derivatives $(C_6H_5CH_2)_2TeX_2$ are known, their molecular adducts with nitrogen donor molecules are less known^{1,2}. The present communication deals with the synthesis of dibenzyltellurium(IV) derivatives molecular adducts. Fifteen compounds of the type R_2TeX_2L (where $X = I, NO_3, CN$ and SCN ; $L = 2,2'$ -dipyridyl, 1,10-phenanthroline and neocuproine) have been synthesised and characterised.

Results and Discussion

All the molecular adducts were stable in air. The elemental analysis data and the molar conductance data ($40-58 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$ in DMF) suggested that they are nonelectrolyte³ with composition of $R_2TeX_2.L$. Pronounced shifting of $\nu_{C=N}$ frequency by $30-85 cm^{-1}$ towards lower region in all these compounds as compared to the free ligands ($1620-1640 cm^{-1}$) suggests the involvement of pyridine-nitrogen in coordination⁴. Far-ir spectra of all the compounds exhibited bands at $420-410 (Te-N)^1$ and $560-540 (Te-C)^5$. The dithiocyanate compounds showed bands at about $2100 (CN)$, $710 (CS)$ and $415 cm^{-1} (NCS)$, which clearly indicate coordinated S-bonded thiocyanato group^{6,7}. The nitrate compounds showed a monodentate bonding mode of nitrate in the complexes⁷⁻⁹. The XPS binding energy data of $Te3d_{3/2}$ and $Te3d_{5/2}$ photoelectron peaks for $(C_6H_5CH_2)_2TeX_2$ were observed at ~ 584.0 and $\sim 574.0 eV$ respectively, higher than their molecular adducts $(C_6H_5CH_2)_2TeX_2.L$ 582.6 and $572.6 eV$. Further, N1s binding energies of the donor ligand (L)

in the metal complexes were more positive than their free donor ligand. These XPS data suggested that donor ligand (L) are coordinated to tellurium metal ion¹⁰.

Experimental

Dibenzyltellurium(IV) derivatives were prepared, purified and characterised according to literature procedure¹. $(C_6H_5CH_2)_2TeX_2$ (where $X = I, CN, SCN, NO_3$) (1 mmol) dissolved in chloroform (20 ml) was refluxed with 1 mmol of 2,2'-bipyridine or phenanthroline or neocuproine (1 mmol) for 3-4 h. The solution was then distilled off and the concentrated solution was allowed to stay overnight in freeze. The resulting crystals were washed with petroleum ether (b.p. $60-80^\circ$) and dried under reduced pressure.

Conductance measurements were done in DMF at room temperature using a Digisun electronic conductivity bridge. Infrared spectra (CsI) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 883 spectrophotometer. X-Ray photoelectron spectra (XPS) were recorded on a VG Scientific ESCA-3 MK II electron spectrometer. The $AlK\alpha$ line ($1486.6 eV$) was used for photoexcitation. The $Cu2p_{3/2}$ ($BE = 932.8 \pm 0.2 eV$) and $Au4f_{7/2}$ ($BE = 83.8 \pm 0.1 eV$) lines were used to calibrate the instrument and $Ag3d_{5/2}$ ($BE = 368.2 eV$) was used for cross-checking. All the spectra were recorded using the same spectrometer parameter of 50 eV pass energy and 4 mm slit width. The reduced full-width at half-maximum (FWHM) at $Au4f_{7/2}$ ($BE = 83.8 eV$) level under this condition was 1.2 eV.

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